

VALKYRIES

D1.4 Protocols for innovators

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable provides methodological protocols for innovators to meet compliance requirements while developing technological solutions for first responders.

2. Identification

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3. Document and Project Scope

This is the first version of the Protocols for Innovators that will be submitted in its final one at M24 aiming to drive the ethical-legal compliance in Research & Development & Innovation sectors.

Starting from the procedures developed in VALKYRIES, the document aims to share a pathway towards the so-called accountability in each step of the life-cycle of the development despite of the type of the designed technology or solution.

3.1. Project Overview

The Deliverable combines the research and compliance overview of the VALKYRIES ecosystem. It shows how regulation, standardisation, and compliance are fully integrated by the application of the principle of accountability.

3.2. Document Structure

Starting from the VALKYRIES ethical-legal compliance experience, the document firstly illustrates how the evolution of the regulatory framework, and the standardisation of technical steps are impacting on the compliance activities, then it provides protocols to drive innovators towards the complexity of the applicable framework.

4. Ethical legal compliance and the regulatory framework

Ethical-legal compliance activities play a crucial role in the Research & Development & Innovation sectors, where innovators are the main agents. In fact, in parallel to the technical steps, each technological solution shall be compliant with the applicable framework *by design* and *by default*. To this end, the so-called risk-based approach governs the implementation of identified organisational and technical measures considered as proper ones to meet the ethical requirements and to fulfil the legal obligations. In particular, the innovators shall assess how their idea is impacting on fundamental rights and therefore they shall accomplish to the provisions stated by applicable framework to protect them. Compliance activities are usually consisting of the introduction of technical and organisational measures in the life-cycle of the technology development either to mitigate the risks of their infringement of fundamental rights or to fulfil the stated obligations. The innovators shall be able to demonstrate to have adopted the described methodology (i.e. accountability). In case of breach of stated obligations, they could be sanctioned by the competent authority and considered as liable for possible occurred damages.

Beyond the illustrated premises, the ethical-legal compliance process is particularly complex, if we consider the following barriers:

- Innovators are not always familiar with fundamental rights protection as they are interpreted by the ethical-legal framework.
- The ethical-legal binding framework is often unclear also for experts because the state of the art is still evolving and national implementations may limit a harmonised sectorial approach.

In particular, the EU Regulations, that are directly binding among EU Member States, could leave room for national implementations and interpretations. This could limit a harmonised interpretation of a given provision. The EU Directives, indeed, become effective in a given EU Member States only after a national legislative implementation, potentially determining 27 different procedures to interpret the same principle.

- Regarding soft law regulations, such as recommendations, guidelines etc, even if they are non-binding, as they aim to address interpretative issues, they could contribute to the state of the art on a given topic. In fact, to follow specific soft law provisions could help to demonstrate an accountable approach, especially if they have been adopted by supra-national institutional organisations (e.g. European Data Protection Board -EDPB-, European Union Agency for Cybersecurity, other groups of experts), or national ones (like Data Protection Authorities), or as a self-regulation instrument by private companies in a given sector (e.g. certificates under article 42 GDPR). Such a standardisation activity regarding interpretative gaps could stimulate the ongoing legislative debates, but - at the same time - it could arise several procedural differences to meet the same ethical-legal requirements.

This document aims to identify methodological solutions by developing protocols for innovators in order to facilitate the compliance activities starting from the ethical-legal issues arisen in the VALKYRIES ecosystem.

From this perspective, this protocol illustrates actions that are supposed to be undertaken by innovators to be compliant with the binding framework and accountable respect to the non-binding one. The adoption of the following protocols will also facilitate the development of best

practices that could contribute to a more standardised and harmonised development of the ethical-legal framework in the future, especially in cross-border contexts.

4.1. Overview of the regulatory initiatives for R&D&I

In the last years the EU adopted several strategies to boost innovation. In particular, all the initiatives are based on distributing roles and responsibilities in order to undertake an impact assessment of the technological solution on fundamental rights protected by the EU Charter on Fundamental Rights.

The introduction of a risk-based approach to drive innovation constitutes the common core of the legislative initiatives that have been drafted in the last years. However, the plurality of aspects relating to the ethical-legal compliance are not always addressed with the same technical and organisational measures. In fact, R&D&I sectors shall address several challenges from the ones related to common market and business development, to the ones related to the data-driven approach to open data, data spaces development and privacy.

The table below includes an overview of the regulatory framework impacting on the ethical legal challenges related to R&D&I sectors.

Act	Comments
Regulation (EU) no 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (CTR)	Applicable since January 31 st 2022.
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since May 25th 2018. - Room for national implementations for research (article 89). - Room for national implementation for “sensitive data” processing (article 9). - First binding provision on automated decision-making processing (article 22).
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since 2019 - Processing different non-personal datasets could make them considered as personal data
Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (MDR)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since May 21st 2021. - The former Directive had national implementations in each Member State. - Local ethics committees developed own procedures, developing barriers to harmonised application of the law in action. - Legal gap between approval procedures for clinical trials and non-clinical studies.
Regulation (EU) 2022/868 of the European Parliament and of the	- Applicable since September 2023.

Act	Comments
Council of 30 May 2022 on European data governance and amending Regulation (EU) 2018/1724 (Data Governance Act, DGA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Field of application mainly refers to public sector, but it aims to set-up common European data spaces in strategic domains, involving both private and public players, for health, environment, energy, agriculture, mobility, finance, manufacturing, public administration. - National policies for data altruism.
Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It specifies the role and mandate of ENISA. - It introduces a European system for the certification of the IT security of devices connected to the Internet and other digital products and services.
Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts COM/2021/206 final (AI Act)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It is still not binding. - It recalls the above-mentioned legislative initiatives but players are not completely overlapping in terms of roles and responsibilities.
Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on machinery products COM/2021/202 final	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - It refers to safety of products not based on AI techniques. - It recalls the above-mentioned legislative initiatives but players are not completely overlapping in terms of roles and responsibilities.
Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Entered into force in 24 April 2011, and it was expected to be transposed to national law by the EU Member States by 25 October 2013. - The Directive is principally addressed to patients, as it aims to regulate the conditions under which such private players can travel to other EU countries for medical care. In this context, it tackles with the need for a secure and efficient cooperation between national healthcare systems across Europe, hence it encourages Member States to adopt measures respecting data privacy of patients while facilitating the exchange of health data.
Regulation (EU) 2014/910 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applicable since 17 September 2014. - It is intended to provide for a securely and smoothly operation system of interaction between public and private players, including business enterprises and citizens, across EU.

Table 1 – Overview of the regulatory initiatives for R&D&I

5. Ethical legal compliance and standardisation

Ethical-legal compliance is a complex and continuous process where -according to a predetermined and distributed system of roles and responsibilities- innovators must introduce safeguards and procedures in the technical development of a given solution, in order to mitigate risks to infringe fundamental rights and/or to accomplish to specific binding provisions.

Ethical-legal compliance is strictly connected to regulation and standardisation processes. In fact, the binding dimension of the statutory law for innovators is completed by the global character of the technical standards that strongly impact on the law in action and, more generally, on soft law tools. However, considering the regulatory barriers identified in the previous paragraph, the case-by-case approach could still be combined with a more harmonised approach aiming to identify the ethical legal dimension as a part of the development of technical standards.

The VALKYRIES consortium is focusing on these profiles, combining the strict compliance of the project activities with the ambition to develop standardised procedure aiming to develop a *modus operandi* suitable to be applied in any R&D activity.

5.1. Overview of the standards

The table below identifies for each regulatory initiative the good practices, standards and tools that have been developed to achieve a higher level of accountability.

They are not binding and they are addressing only specific profiles, but they cover interpretative gaps, addressing how to comply with ethics by design and by default.

Act	Legal standards and tools
Regulation (EU) no 536/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 on clinical trials on medicinal products for human use, and repealing Directive 2001/20/EC (CTR)	ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation GDPR)	ENISA 2019 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/risk-level-tool/risk CNIL 2019 https://www.cnil.fr/en/gdpr-toolkit ENISA 2020 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme/ CNIL 2022 https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle/ia-comment-etre-en-conformite-avec-le-rgpd ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Regulation (EU) 2018/1807 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 on a framework for the free flow	COMMUNICATION FROM THE COMMISSION TO THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL Guidance on the Regulation on a framework for the free flow of non-personal data in the European Union https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM:2019:250:FIN

Act	Legal standards and tools
of non-personal data in the European Union	
Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, amending Directive 2001/83/EC, Regulation (EC) No 178/2002 and Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 and repealing Council Directives 90/385/EEC and 93/42/EEC (MDR)	ENISA 2020 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/publications/eucs-cloud-service-scheme/ ENISA https://www.enisa.europa.eu/topics/critical-information-infrastructures-and-services/health/good-practices-for-the-security-of-healthcare-services#/
Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act)	ENISA 2022 https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/taking-care-of-health-data
Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the council laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (artificial intelligence act) and amending certain union legislative acts COM/2021/206 final (AI Act)	CNIL 2022 https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle/ia-comment-etre-en-conformite-avec-le-rgpd ALTAI 2020 https://digitalstrategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence-altai-self-assessment
Directive 2011/24/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 9 March 2011 on the application of patients' rights in cross-border healthcare	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commission Delegated Decision of 10 March 2014 setting out criteria and conditions that European Reference Networks and healthcare providers wishing to join a European Reference Network must fulfil, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32014D0286&from=EN ; - Commission Implementing Decision of 10 March 2014 setting out criteria for establishing and evaluating European Reference Networks and their Members and for facilitating the exchange of information and expertise on establishing and evaluating such Networks, https://eur-

Act	Legal standards and tools
	<p>lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:32014D0287&from=EN;</p> <p>- Directorate-General for Health and Food Safety Guidelines on Patient Summary (3 June 2021), https://health.ec.europa.eu/publications/guidelines-patient-summary_en</p>
Regulation (EU) 2014/910 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 on electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market and repealing Directive 1999/93/EC	-Commission Recommendation on a European Electronic Health Record Exchange Format (C(2019)800) of 6 February 2019 (and the Annex https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019H0243&rid=2)

Table 2 – Overview of the standards

6. Protocol for innovators

Considering the above-illustrated aspects, the following protocol, including innovator-friendly check-lists could be extracted to facilitate the adoption of an accountable approach in each step of the innovative solution development, namely: 1. Preparatory activities; 2. Development; 3. Application/Usage. This is a preliminary document to be validated and integrated at M24.

6.1. Preparatory activities

This step refers to the *design* of the innovative solution and it determines the beginning of the life-cycle of the solution. Preparatory activities could be embedded in a proposal /draft of project that includes the proof of concept of the technology solution. In that context, innovators shall assess if and how the development could impact on fundamental rights protection and how to comply with the corresponding ethical-legal framework. This step is needed both for *management* and *technical* purposes. In fact, both human and technical resources as well as time shall be allocated to the ethical-legal compliance.

To better achieve a realistic evaluation of the compliance activities, innovators need to firstly identify the targeted group / end-users as well as the different applications/uses of the technological solution in order to provide a first screening of the applicable ethical legal framework and select the main issues that shall be addressed as well as the obligations they need to accomplish to during the development. Two dimensions shall be analysed: i) the impact during the development of the technology (*compliance by design*) and ii) the impact once on the market (*compliance by default*).

The following check-list could be identified.

A) Compliance by design. In order to develop/test the solution:

1. Do you need to involve human participants?

If not, an information sheet including the privacy information (see below) is required under articles 11 ff GDPR, and an informed consent could be required under the national legal framework.

If yes, are they belonging to vulnerable groups (i.e. patients, children, employees etc)?

- An ethical committee approval is required for clinical trials.
- An ethical committee approval could be binding under national/sectorial legal frameworks even for non-clinical trials.
- Further requirements could be necessary to ask a valid informed consent (e.g. trade union agreement, parents' consent, etc) under national/sectorial legal frameworks.

2. Do you need to process personal data?

If yes, a privacy information under articles 11 ff GDPR is required.

3. Are processed data belonging to special categories under article 9 GDPR?

If yes, check if it is binding under the national/sectorial applicable legal framework to:

- Submit a protocol before the competent ethical committee.
- Undertake a data protection impact assessment under article 35 GDPR.

- Introduce specific technical and organisational measures as defined by the law.

4. Do you need to involve animals?

If yes, check:

- 3Rs requirements are fulfilled
- An ethical protocol shall be submitted under the national/sectorial legal framework.

B) Compliance by default. In order to put the technology on the market:

1. Check if any authorisation to use it is required at EU, national, local level, you will need to undertake required actions to obtain it. They may include:
 - a. To submit technical information on the developed technology.
 - b. To submit the approval from the competent ethical committee.
 - c. To pay fees.
 - d. To undertake actions within given delays.

Suggestions for the preliminary compliance activities:

- ➔ Ask for a specialistic ethical-legal advice
- ➔ Allocate time, human resources, costs in the workplan

6.2. Development

This step refers to the workplan development for a technology solution. According to the risk-based approach a continuous assessment of the impact on fundamental rights shall be introduced in the life-cycle in order to be able to identify and properly implement technical and organisational safeguards to mitigate the risks identified in the preparatory activities step as well as to take actions in order to accomplish to the binding provisions stated in the applicable ethical-legal framework.

The following checklist could be followed in the development of the workplan either for the *by design* dimension or for the *by default* one.

1. Mapping the ethical legal framework applicable to the given technology. In particular, verify whether you need to comply with EU Regulations / Directives and national implementations regarding:
 - Personal data under EU Regulation 2016/679, considering the following grounds:
 - i. Purposes and means of data processing to establish how to protect the availability, confidentiality, and integrity of data.
 - ii. Nature of data to combine GDPR conditions with possible national safeguards in case of “sensitive data”.
 - iii. Legal basis of data also to establish the governance in case of multi-party sharing.
 - iv. Conditions to process cross-border data flows.

- v. Conditions for the possible secondary use of data to check legal basis, governance, safeguards (e.g. pseudonymisation).
- vi. Contents for the privacy information to data subjects.
- Non-personal data flows under the EU Regulation 2018/1807, considering the following grounds:
 - i. Conditions to give/obtain access to data (IPRs, data ownership, etc.).
 - ii. Conditions to give/obtain access to confidential information.
 - iii. Conditions to boost open data, by developing a FAIR ecosystem where data are as open as possible (i.e. Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and as close as necessary (i.e. to protect confidentiality and privacy).
- Non-personal data flows under the Data Governance Act
 - i. Conditions for data altruism.
 - ii. Conditions for public services intermediaries.
- Artificial Intelligence.
 - i. If AI Act has entered into force, then meet the requirements.
 - ii. If AI Act has not entered into force yet, then undertake an assessment adopting a common tool (e.g. the ALTAI checklist, CNIL tool) to deal with the requirements of lawfulness, ethics, and robustness of the developed technology.
- Cybersecurity
 - i. If any standards or certifications have been adopted
 - Check if you will need to formally adhere to them to put the technology on the market.
 - In any case, check the requirements and apply them to your impact assessment as best standard to achieve accountability.
- Clinical Trials and non-clinical studies with volunteers
 - i. If a clinical study shall be developed
 - Assign time and resources to comply with the CTR and to follow local practices under the competent ethics committee.
 - Develop a protocol including the following sections:
 - a. Identification of roles and responsibilities between sponsor, sponsor-investigator, Principal investigator, etc.
 - b. Title of the study.
 - c. Background and rationale.
 - d. Objectives and Outcomes.
 - e. Design.
 - f. Population.
 - g. Assessments of *sub d,e,f*.
 - h. Safety.
 - i. Statistical method.
 - j. Data management plan (including IPRs and Data protection profiles).
 - k. Quality assurance and control.
 - l. Publication and Dissemination policy.
 - m. Funding and support.

- n. Insurance.
 - o. References.
 - p. Annexes (informed consent templates including privacy policy, Conflict of interests declaration, agreements between organisations involved in the trial).
- ii. If a non-clinical trial shall be developed
 - Assign time and resources to follow local practices under the competent ethics committee.
 - Develop a protocol including the above-illustrated sections, namely: a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j,k,l,m,n,o,p if required by the specific study.
2. Implement the technical and organisational measures required by the applicable legal framework.
 3. Establish mechanisms to monitor an effective implementation of the measures and safeguards identified under sub 2.

Suggestions for the compliance activities:

- ➔ Establish a concrete dialogue between ethical-legal experts and technical staff
- ➔ Introduce monitoring systems to verify the alignment between compliance activities and technical development of the technology

6.3. Application/Usage

During the application/usage of the developed technology sectorial legislations could require maintaining an accountable approach to monitor the ethical dimensions in order to avoid either misuse/dual use or to ensure fundamental rights protection in the concrete application usage of the developed technology. If the developer is providing services to the end user or the technology works on servers belonging to the developer, then the latter is maintaining a control on it, and in particular on data processed by the technology. Such a role shall be identified, regulated, and communicated to the end user. Therefore, compliance activities are required also at this stage. To this end, the following checklist could be useful to maintain an accountable approach also when the product is ready to be placed on the market.

1. Roles identification.
 - a. If the developer processes personal data as a data controller, then comply with the GDPR as above-described.
 - b. If the developer processes personal data as data processor/joint data controller, then enter into a data processing agreement with the data controller.
 - c. If the developer performs as a system administrator, then check if any appointments / conditions are required.
 - d. Repeat compliance activities for any secondary use of data.
2. End-users/data subjects' consent and rights.
 - a. Terms and conditions shall include a section dedicated to privacy information on personal data processing (where applicable).

- b. Check if the consent is the legal basis of the data processing. In that case, introduce features to verify the identity in the consent collection/management procedures.
 - c. Introduce features to make data subjects able to exercise their rights.
 - d. Adapt interfaces and contents to the vulnerability of the data subject and to the possible further uses of data, in particular:
 - i. if end-users are children, then check age for directly providing the service, otherwise include mechanisms to engage legal representatives.
 - ii. if end-users are patients / potential patients, then adapt information to the purposes of the technology and to the context.
3. Monitoring and reporting mechanisms.
- a. Introduce monitoring mechanisms to check the updates to empower technology trustworthiness.
 - b. Introduce reporting mechanisms for users.

Suggestions for the compliance activities:

- ➔ Compare Terms and Conditions with other applied for similar technologies
- ➔ Engage stakeholders / end users' representatives to evaluate the efficacy of the features introduced for consent collection and management

7. Conclusions

This document developed a protocol to address ethical legal compliance activities in Research and Innovation sectors. In particular, it includes checklists to deal with possible ethical-legal issues emerging during a given life-cycle of the development of a not-specified technological solution in order to achieve a high level of compliance by design and by default.

Smart boxes suggest best practices to concretely apply the instructions.

8. Annex A – References and bibliography

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4. Annex B – Glossary

Acronym	Description
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
AI	Artificial Intelligence

Table 3 - Glossary